

Vertex version of pi index of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons PAH_K

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Abstract Let $G=(V,E)$ be a simple connected molecular graph. *Khadikar et.al.* introduced the *PI* index defined by $PI_v(G) = \sum_{e=uv \in E(G)} (n_v(e|G) + n_u(e|G))$, where $n_u(e|G)$ is the number of vertices of G lying closer to u and $n_u(e|G)$ is the number of vertices of G lying closer to v . In this paper, we compute a closed formula of vertex PI index for Polycyclic Aromatic hydrocarbons.

Keywords Poly Aromatic Hydrocarbons *PAH_K*; PI index; Cut Method; Orthogonal Cut.

Introduction

Let G be a simple molecular graph such that its vertices set $V(G)$ and edge set $E(G)$ corresponds to the atoms and bonds respectively. In graph theory, d_v is the degree of a vertex $v \in V(G)$, the number of adjacent vertices with v or the size of first neighborhood of vertex v . An edge $e=uv$ of graph G is attached between two vertices u and v . The distance between two vertices $u, v \in V(G)$ is equal to the number of edges on shortest path between them and it is denoted by $d(u,v)$.

A topological index is a numerical quantity associated with graph G . In mathematical chemistry, many topological indices are introduced so far. For any molecular graph G they are invariant on the graph automorphism.

H. Wiener [1] defined the notion of the *Wiener index* and defined as:

$$W(G) = \sum_{\{u,v\} \in V(G)} d(u,v)$$

I. Gutman et. al. [2,3] defined the vertex and edge versions of *Szeged index*, which are defined as

$$Sz_v(G) = \sum [n_u(e|G) \times n_v(e|G)]$$

$$Sz_e(G) = \sum_{e=uv \in E(G)} (m_u(e|G) + m_v(e|G))$$

where $n_u(e|G)$ and $m_u(e|G)$ represents the number of vertices of G lying closer to u than to v and $m_u(e|G)$ is the number of edges of G lying closer to u than to v , respectively, analogously $n_v(e|G)$ and $m_v(w|G)$.

Khadikar [4] and *Ashrafi* [8] proposed the edge and vertex versions of *Padmakar-Ivan index* (PI). These versions of PI index of a graph G is defined as:

$$PI_e(G) = \sum_{e \in E(G)} (m_u(e|G) + m_v(e|G))$$

$$PI_v(G) = \sum_{e \in E(G)} (n_u(e|G) + n_v(e|G))$$

See the paper series for further details [4-9].

Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons

PAH_k considered here is a family of such hydrocarbons containing several copies of benzene on circumference and is ubiquitous products. Polyaromatic hydrocarbons can be pictured as a small piece of graphene sheets with the free valences of dangling bond saturated by H *vice versa*, which can be interpreted as an infinite PAH molecule. These type of molecules has utilization in modeling graphite surface [10-16].

Main Result:

Let PAH_k be the *Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons* ($\forall k \geq 1$). Then the *PI* index of PAH_k is equal to:

$$PI_v(PAH_k) = 18k^2(k+1)[18k^2 + 9k - 1]$$

Proof. Consider the general representation of the Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons PAH_k ($\forall k \geq 1$) as shown in Figure 1, we see that PAH_k has $6k^2 + 6k$ vertices/atoms and $9k^2 + 3k$ edge/bonds ($|E(PAH_k)|$), such that $6k^2$ of its vertices are Carbon atoms with three bonds and $6k$ of its vertices are Hydrogen atoms with one bond.

Figure 1: All orthogonal cuts of PAH_k .

Our aim is to compute the *PI* index of the *Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons* PAH_k . So, we cut PAH_k and see that for an arbitrary edge cut $e=uv$ ($e \in E(PAH_k)$), there is an orthogonal cut $C(e)$.

One can see that for i^{th} orthogonal cut C_i ($\forall i=0,1,2,\dots,k$); there are $k+i$ co-distance edges of PAH_k , and this implies that for all edge $e=uv \in C_i \subset E(PAH_k)$, there are $k+i$ repetitions of the vertex partitions $N_u(e|PAH_k)$ and $N_v(e|PAH_k)$ such that

$$n_v(e|PAH_k) = |\{x| x \in V(PAH_k), d(v,x) < d(x,u)\}| = i^2 + 2(k+1)i + k.$$

From Figure 1, it's easy to see that for all edge $e=uv \in E(PAH_k)$, $N(e|PAH_k) = \emptyset$ and $n(e|PAH_k) = 0$. Thus

$$|V(PAH_k)| = n(e|PAH_k) + n_v(e|PAH_k) + n_u(e|PAH_k) \text{ and } n_u(e|PAH_k) = |V(PAH_k)| - n_v(e|PAH_k).$$

Therefore,

$$n_u(e|PAH_k) = \{x| x \in V(PAH_k), d(u,x) < d(x,v)\} = 6k^2 + 5k - i^2 - 2(k+1)i$$

Now by using the above calculations, we can compute the *PI* index of the Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons PAH_k ($\forall k \geq 1$) as follow:

$$PI_v(PAH_k) = \sum_{e=uv \in E(PAH_k)} (n_v(e|PAH_k) + n_u(e|PAH_k))$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= 6 \sum_{e=uv \in C_0} (k) (n_v(e | PAH_k) + n_u(e | PAH_k)) \\
&+ 6 \sum_{e=uv \in C_1} (k+1) (n_v(e | PAH_k) + n_u(e | PAH_k)) \\
&+ \dots \\
&+ 6 \sum_{e=uv \in C_{k-1}} (2k-1) (n_v(e | PAH_k) + n_u(e | PAH_k)) \\
&+ 3 \sum_{e=uv \in C_k} (2k) (n_v(e | PAH_k) + n_u(e | PAH_k)) \\
&= 6k \sum_{e=uv \in C_k} |V(PAH_k)| + 6 \sum_{\substack{e=uv \in C_i \\ i=0,1,\dots,k-1}} (k+i) |V(PAH_k)| \\
&= 6 |V(PAH_k)| \left[k \sum_{e=uv \in C_k} + \sum_{\substack{e=uv \in C_i \\ i=0,1,\dots,k-1}} (k+i) \right] \\
&= 6 (6k^2 + 6k) \left[k (9k^2 + 3k) + k^2 + \frac{k(k-1)}{2} \right] \\
&= 36k(k+1) \left[\frac{18k^3 + 6k^2 + 3k^2 - k}{2} \right] \\
&= 18k(k+1) [18k^3 + 9k^2 - k] \\
&= 18k^2(k+1) [18k^2 + 9k - 1]
\end{aligned}$$

And this completes the proof of theorem. ■

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